

Validation of a continuum cathode-side model for multi-product CO₂ electroreduction in gas diffusion electrodes

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Abstract

Gas-diffusion-electrode (GDE) CO₂ electrolyzers can reach high current densities, but their operation is governed by coupled gas transport, electrolyte chemistry, intermediate formation and competing hydrogen evolution. This proceeding summarises the validation of a two-dimensional cathode-side continuum model for multi-product CO₂ electroreduction in a GDE flow reactor. The model couples gas-phase flow, multicomponent gas transport, gas-liquid transfer, Nernst-Planck electrolyte transport, homogeneous carbonate chemistry and Butler-Volmer-based electrochemical pathways in which CO links CO₂ conversion to downstream C₂₊ products. Validation against an internally consistent experimental dataset shows quantitative agreement for the CO₂-to-CO pathway across kinetic and transport-influenced regimes, while also capturing the emergence of HER and C₂H₄ formation at more negative cathode potentials. These comparisons provide the basis for using the model to analyse how local reactant availability, intermediate formation and gaseous product generation affect GDE reactor operation.

Keywords

CO₂ electroreduction, gas diffusion electrodes, continuum modelling, gas-phase transport, electrochemical engineering, validation

1 Introduction

Electrochemical CO₂ reduction offers a route to convert renewable electricity and CO₂ into carbon-containing fuels and chemical feedstocks [3, 4]. Gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) have become central to this field because they supply gaseous CO₂ directly to the catalyst layer and thereby enable current densities well above those attainable in conventional aqueous batch cells, where CO₂

solubility limits reactant supply [2, 6, 9]. However, GDE operation also introduces coupled transport and phase-distribution effects. Gas access, electrolyte penetration, catalyst-layer wetting, ionic conduction and product removal must remain balanced, particularly under high-current-density operation.

For Cu-based catalysts, this coupling becomes especially important because product formation is not limited to a single carbon product. CO₂ can be reduced to CO, while CO can act as an upstream intermediate for downstream C₂₊ products such as C₂H₄ and oxygenates [5, 7]. At the same time, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) competes for current and generates gaseous H₂. The resulting reactor behaviour depends not only on intrinsic catalytic selectivity, but also on the local availability of CO₂, the generation and consumption of CO, and the accumulation of gaseous products.

Continuum models provide a useful framework for interpreting these coupled phenomena because they resolve local concentration, potential and reaction-rate gradients that are difficult to measure experimentally [1]. The aim of this proceeding is deliberately narrow: to summarise the rationale and validation of a cathode-side continuum model for multi-product CO₂ electroreduction in a GDE flow reactor. The focus is on validation against three product-current trends: the CO₂-to-CO pathway, HER and the CO-to-C₂H₄ pathway. These comparisons establish the model as a basis for subsequent analysis of transport-reaction coupling and local reactant/intermediate availability in high-current-density GDE operation.

2 Reactor configuration and modelling approach

The model represents the cathodic compartment of a flow electrochemical reactor equipped with a gas diffusion electrode. The simulated geometry corresponds to a two-dimensional longitudinal cross-section containing the gas flow channel, the gas diffusion electrode and the electrolyte flow channel. This representation was selected to retain the main gradients along the electrode length and across the gas-liquid interface while keeping the model computationally tractable for reactor-scale analysis.

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Table 1: Main geometric and operating parameters used in the model.

Parameter	Value
Electrode height	25 mm
Electrode width	20 mm
Gas flow channel thickness	3 mm
Electrolyte flow channel thickness	4 mm
Gas diffusion layer thickness	80 μm
Catalyst layer thickness	3.6 μm
Gas feed	Pure CO_2
Gas flow rate	12 ml min^{-1}
Electrolyte feed	1 M KOH
Electrolyte flow rate	15 ml min^{-1}
Temperature	25°C
Pressure	1 atm

The catalyst layer was represented as a reactive boundary between the gas diffusion layer and electrolyte channel, rather than as a separate micrometre-thick porous domain. This boundary treatment follows the purpose of the present model: to describe the coupling between gas-phase supply, gas–liquid transfer, electrolyte transport and electrochemical product formation at the reactor scale.

The simulated system is based on an experimental GDE flow reactor previously reported for CO_2 electroreduction to C_2H_4 [8]. The electrode consists of a PTFE-based gas diffusion layer, a sputtered Cu film and a porous carbon-supported mixed-copper-oxide catalyst layer. The electrolyte is 1 M KOH, supplied through the electrolyte flow channel, while pure CO_2 is fed through the gas channel. The main geometric and operating parameters used in the model are summarised in Table 1.

The model is formulated under isothermal conditions. The gas phase is treated as ideal, laminar and compressible, with density and viscosity updated from the local gas composition. The electrolyte is treated as an incompressible single-phase liquid. The gas diffusion layer is considered hydrophobic, while the catalyst layer is represented through an effective wetted interfacial region where gas–liquid transfer and electrochemical reactions occur. Bubble nucleation, electrolyte flooding and explicit membrane/anode transport are not included in this short validation study.

3 Governing model

3.1 Gas-phase flow and species transport

Gas flow in the gas channel is described using the compressible mass and momentum balances

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = S, \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}, \quad (2)$$

where ρ , \mathbf{u} , p , S and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ are the gas density, velocity, pressure, net mass source and viscous stress tensor, respectively. Flow through the porous GDE is described using a Brinkman formulation, which adds porous-media resistance to the gas momentum balance,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\varepsilon_{\text{GDE}} \rho) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = S_{\text{GDE}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_{\text{GDE}}} \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\varepsilon_{\text{GDE}}} \right] = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon_{\text{GDE}}} \boldsymbol{\tau} \right) - \frac{\mu}{\kappa_{\text{GDE}}} \mathbf{u}, \quad (4)$$

where ε_{GDE} , κ_{GDE} and μ are the GDE porosity, permeability and gas viscosity.

The gas species balance is written in terms of mass fraction ω_i ,

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \omega_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \omega_i \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_i + S_i, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{j}_i is the diffusive mass flux and S_i is the source term associated with interfacial transfer and electrochemical production or consumption. Multicomponent diffusion is described using a Maxwell–Stefan formulation. In the porous GDE, effective diffusivities are corrected for porosity and tortuosity, and wall interactions are represented through Knudsen diffusion. This treatment allows the local gas mixture to change as CO_2 is consumed and gaseous products such as CO , C_2H_4 and H_2 are generated.

3.2 Liquid-phase transport and carbonate chemistry

The electrolyte velocity field is obtained from the incompressible continuity equation,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0. \quad (6)$$

Dissolved species are transported by diffusion, migration and convection using the Nernst–Planck flux,

$$\mathbf{N}_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i u_{m,i} F c_i \nabla \phi_L + c_i \mathbf{u}, \quad (7)$$

where D_i , c_i , z_i , $u_{m,i}$ and ϕ_L are the diffusivity, concentration, charge number, mobility and electrolyte potential of species i . The corresponding species balance is:

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{N}_i = S_i. \quad (8)$$

Electroneutrality is imposed in the electrolyte,

$$\sum_i z_i c_i = 0. \quad (9)$$

Homogeneous reactions among dissolved CO_2 , HCO_3^- , CO_3^{2-} , H^+ and OH^- are included to describe carbonate chemistry under alkaline conditions. For a reversible homogeneous reaction r , the net rate is written as

$$R_r = k_{r,f} \prod_{i \in \text{reactants}} c_i^{|v_{r,i}|} - k_{r,b} \prod_{i \in \text{products}} c_i^{|v_{r,i}|}. \quad (10)$$

This reaction set accounts for the rapid redistribution of absorbed CO_2 into bicarbonate and carbonate species and for the associated consumption or generation of OH^- .

3.3 Gas–liquid transfer and charge conservation

Transport of gaseous reactants and products across the gas–liquid interface is described using an effective thin-film expression,

$$J_{i,G-L} = -D_{i,G-L} \frac{c_{i,G-L}^t - c_{i,G-L}^*}{\delta_{G-L}}, \quad (11)$$

where $J_{i,G-L}$ is the interfacial molar flux, $D_{i,G-L}$ is the effective diffusivity, $c_{i,G-L}^t$ is the concentration at the electrolyte side of the transfer region and $c_{i,G-L}^*$ is the equilibrium concentration at the gas–liquid interface. Henry’s law is used to define $c_{i,G-L}^* = p_i H_i$, where p_i is the gas partial pressure and H_i is Henry’s constant. The effective transfer length δ_{G-L} is taken as the catalyst-layer thickness, representing an effective reactor-scale resistance for the fairly wet and tortuous catalyst layer used for validation.

Charge transport in the electronically conducting GDE is described using Ohm’s law,

$$\mathbf{i}_{\text{GDE}} = -\sigma_{\text{GDE}} \nabla \phi_{\text{GDE}}, \quad (12)$$

while the electrolyte current density is obtained from the charged-species fluxes,

$$i_L = F \sum_i z_i N_i. \quad (13)$$

At the reactive boundary, the electronic and ionic current balances are coupled through the sum of the local electrochemical partial current densities.

3.4 Electrochemical reactions and apparent kinetics

The electrochemical network is represented by lumped cathodic pathways for CO₂-to-CO, CO-to-C₂H₄ and HER,

These reactions are not intended as elementary surface mechanisms. They provide an apparent kinetic representation of the experimentally observed product pathways and allow the model to couple local CO₂ availability, CO formation and downstream C₂H₄ production.

For reaction j , the cathodic partial current density is calculated using a simplified Butler–Volmer/Tafel expression,

$$i_j = -i_{j,\text{ref}}^e g_{j,c} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha_{j,c} F}{RT} \eta_j\right), \quad (17)$$

where $i_{j,\text{ref}}^e$, $g_{j,c}$, $\alpha_{j,c}$ and η_j are the reference exchange current density, concentration-dependence term, cathodic transfer coefficient and overpotential, respectively. The concentration term is written as

$$g_{j,c} = \prod_{i \in O} \frac{c_i}{c_i + c_i^*}, \quad (18)$$

where c_i^* defines the concentration scale at which local reactant limitation becomes important. This form is used to represent reactant availability without imposing full stoichiometric reaction orders from the lumped overall reactions. Kinetic parameters were fitted to experimental product-current data measured under apparent kinetic control for the same GDE system.

3.5 Numerical implementation

The coupled equations were implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics 6.2. The simulations were solved in stages. First, open-circuit flow and concentration fields were obtained to provide physically consistent initial conditions. Second, the applied cathode potential was imposed, electrochemical reactions were enabled and the model was solved transiently until quasi-steady partial current densities were reached. Because gas density and viscosity depend on the evolving gas composition, the gas-flow solution and electrochemical solution were iterated until changes in current density and velocity field became negligible. The resulting boundary-averaged partial current densities were compared with experimental measurements for the validation cases discussed below.

4 Comparison with experimental product-current trends

The model is compared with experimental partial current densities obtained from the same GDE flow-reactor dataset used to define the geometry, operating conditions and kinetic parameterisation [8]. Three product-current trends are considered in this short proceeding: CO₂-to-CO, HER and CO-to-C₂H₄. These

Figure 1: Experimental and simulated boundary-averaged partial current density for the CO₂-to-CO pathway. The comparison captures both the apparent kinetic region and the deviation from kinetic behaviour as transport limitations become important.

pathways were selected because they test different aspects of the model. The CO₂-to-CO comparison tests whether the model captures the transition from apparent kinetic control toward transport-influenced operation. HER tests the response of the main competing cathodic reaction. The CO-to-C₂H₄ pathway tests whether the reduced reaction network captures the emergence of the dominant multicarbon product observed experimentally.

For the CO₂-to-CO pathway, the model reproduces the increase in partial current density observed experimentally as the cathode potential becomes more negative in the apparent kinetic regime (Figure 1). The model also captures the subsequent deviation from the kinetic trend as CO₂ transport becomes increasingly limiting. This agreement constrains the coupling between gas-phase supply, gas-liquid transfer, electrolyte chemistry and electrochemical consumption of CO₂.

The HER partial current density increases strongly at more negative cathode potentials (Figure 2), as expected for a competing cathodic reaction governed primarily by overpotential and local electrolyte conditions. Capturing this trend is important because HER is not only a parasitic current pathway: it also produces a light gaseous product that can modify gas composition in the GDE and flow channel.

The CO-to-C₂H₄ pathway becomes significant once sufficient cathodic overpotential is applied and CO is available as an intermediate (Figure 3). The model captures the emergence of C₂H₄ as the dominant downstream carbon product over the relevant potential range. This agreement indicates that the reduced kinetic network reproduces the main transition toward C₂+ -dominated operation in the validation system, although it is not intended to provide a complete microkinetic description of all CO-derived products.

Overall, the comparison with these three partial current-density trends shows that the model reproduces the main electrochemical response of the GDE over the potential range considered. The CO₂-to-CO pathway is described with the greatest quantitative accuracy because it is directly linked to CO₂ supply and interfacial transport. The HER and CO-to-C₂H₄ comparisons

Figure 2: Experimental and simulated boundary-averaged partial current density for HER. The model captures the increasing contribution of H_2 generation at more negative cathode potentials.

Figure 3: Experimental and simulated boundary-averaged partial current density for the CO-to- C_2H_4 pathway. The model captures the emergence of C_2H_4 as the dominant downstream carbon product over the relevant potential range.

show that the model also captures the increasing contribution of the competing reaction and the transition toward multicarbon-product formation. Other CO-derived products require more detailed surface-branching descriptions and are not discussed in this short proceeding.

5 Conclusions

A two-dimensional cathode-side continuum model is formulated for multi-product CO_2 electroreduction in a GDE flow reactor. The model combines compressible gas flow, multicomponent gas transport, Nernst–Planck electrolyte transport, homogeneous carbonate chemistry, gas–liquid mass transfer and apparent electrochemical kinetics at a reactive GDE/electrolyte boundary. Comparison with experimental product-current densities shows that the model reproduces the CO_2 -to-CO pathway across kinetic

and transport-influenced regimes and captures the increasing contribution of HER and C_2H_4 formation at more negative cathode potentials. These results establish the model as a suitable basis for analysing coupled transport and reaction phenomena in GDE CO_2 electrolyzers.

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